

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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Abstract

This article collects information about the attention paid to the development of the young generation in our country to become physically and mentally healthy, successful individuals, speech competence in primary classes and its important role in human life. At the same time, the methods of speech formation in children, as well as the opinions of our great scholars about speech are presented.

Key Words

knowledge, speech competence, thinking, pronunciation, syntactic construction, connected speech, written statement, language tool.

It is a fact that does not require proof that science, education and training are the forces that make the country powerful and the nation great. Today, the reforms carried out in our country are aimed at further expanding the coverage of young people with higher education, educating them to be knowledgeable and competent, and training experts in line with world development. It is not for nothing that attention to science has reached a peak in new Uzbekistan. Because now modern life cannot be imagined without the development of science and education. In the leading countries of the world, the development of education is defined as the first task. After all, the future development of the country is closely related to its achievements in this field. The role of minor education, which is the center of science, is incomparable in bringing up the young generation, which is the foundation of our future, mentally healthy, fresh and intelligent. For this reason, the main basis of the reforms is focused on the fundamental reform of preschool education, providing schools with qualified teachers and modern technologies. Therefore, as our wise people say: "Knowledge acquired in youth is like a pattern carved on stone." The first step to the above-mentioned goals is that we start all the knowledge that is given to our children from the primary school.

One of the most important tasks is to strengthen the speech competence of primary school students in primary school. In speech, thought is formed, and at the same time, thought creates speech. "Speech is closely connected with thinking. If there is no speech, there is no thinking, and if there is no material of language, it is impossible to express the thought." Verbal formation of an idea ensures that it is clear, understandable, pure, consistent, and logical. Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on language tools (words, phrases, sentences). Speech performs the function of communication and message, emotional expression and influence of mutual opinion. A well-developed speech serves as one of the important means of a person's active activity in society. For a student, speech is a tool for successful education at school. If the student and his/her language activities are taken into account, speech development means active and practical acquisition of the language in all aspects (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech). In the case of a teacher, speech development means the use of methods and types of work that help students acquire language pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction, and connected speech as an important asset. For speech activity, as well as for the development of students' speech, it is necessary to observe several conditions:

1. There must be a requirement for a person's speech to emerge. The methodical requirement of developing students' speech is to create a situation where the student expresses his opinion, the desire and need to express something verbally or in writing.

2. Any speech should have content and material. The more complete, rich, and valuable this material is, the more meaningful its description will be.

3. An idea is understandable only if it is expressed using words, phrases, sentences, and speech expressions that the listener understands. Therefore, the third condition for successful development of speech is arming speech with language tools. Speech is an important tool in developing students' thinking.

Speech is not only a means of expressing an idea, but also a tool for its formation. Thought serves as the psychological basis of speech, and the condition for its growth is the enrichment of thought. It is possible to successfully develop speech only on the basis of mastering the system of mental activity. That is why great importance is attached to the preparation, improvement of the material, selection of the topic, placement, and logical operations for the development of students' speech. Thought grows successfully only if it is verbally formed and expressed with the help of language material. The concept is expressed by words or phrases, so the concept becomes an important communication material in the word,

which is a language tool. Only if a person knows a word (word combination) that expresses a concept, based on this concept, he has the opportunity to think in external speech.

If we turn to the history of speech culture, we can see many written instructions of our ancestors about speaking correctly and fluently. In particular, thinkers such as Farabi, Zamakhshari, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Kaikovus, Alisher Navoi have noted speech as one of the signs of spiritual perfection in their works. For example, Farabi says about the power of speech: "... the power of speech (speech) is such a power that a person acquires knowledge and skills with the help of it, with the help of which he can distinguish between ugly and beautiful actions in his behavior, and what needs to be done -does things that are not good, and at the same time understands what is harmful and what is useful, what is tasty and what is bitter. Everyone eats, but not everyone eats the same things, and the differences in diet from one culture to the next can be very dramatic. You can let your students share their culture through food by inviting them to talk about or share dishes typical in their countries. To do this, have a cultural food fair or ask your students to prepare a national dish in a class presentation. If everyone in class gets a little taste, even better, just keep in mind food allergies that your students may have.

What better time to talk about traditional foods than during the holidays. Any holiday that pops up on the calendar is an excuse to celebrate any and all holidays from January to December. Ask each of your students to talk about a traditional holiday from their native culture. They can give information about the holiday itself as well as national and family traditions. The students in your class will enjoy sharing some of their traditions as well as hearing about those of their classmates.

Often another element of holidays or special occasions is traditional dress. It is not unusual for ESL students to bring some pieces of formal or traditional dress when they travel overseas to study. If you are teaching immigrants, your students also have a good chance of having these clothing items at home. You can invite your students to wear traditional clothing on a certain day or bring picture of themselves or others in traditional dress. Encourage each person to explain the significance of the different pieces, if any, and give an opportunity for everyone in class to ask questions.

Not only does a country hold particular values, but families also hold certain values that they pass on to their children. Allowing your students to share about their families can open the door to talking about the values that their families hold. Talking about these family values will also often lead to a discussion about the

values of a people group. When opportunities arise for your students to talk about their families, We encourage it and perhaps your students will learn a little more about one another. can say that teaching traditions with such methods will easily help to brush up on language related skills. As culture permeates every aspect of our beings, these topics are just a few that you can use to intentionally bring a discussion of culture into the classroom.

Summarizing the above-mentioned points, it should be noted that the issue of developing the speech of elementary school students is solved in current methodological literature on the basis of different approaches to knowledge about language, vocabulary and speech culture. Based on the linguistic concepts included in the elementary school mother tongue program, exercises can be divided into phonetic, lexical, word formation, morphemic (word composition), graphic, orthographic, orthoepic, grammatical exercises. The analysis carried out on the basis of these exercises is comprehensive in terms of helping students to master theoretical concepts, enriching their vocabulary, developing their connected speech, and provides students with a comprehensive mastery of the language.

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